

replications. Soil was clay loam, with low available N, medium available P and K, and pH 7.5.

Basal CCU (1%) and NCU (5%)

yields were not significantly different from that with PU in splits.

Yields with SCU broadcast and USG deep point placed 2 d after transplanting

were not significantly different from that with split applications of PU.

Split-applied urea was the least expensive practice. □

Applying nitrogen with sesbania

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Yields with and without sesbania green manure and three levels of N as urea in different splits were studied in a field experiment laid out in a randomized complete block design with four replications during 1986 kharif. Soil was a sandy loam (Typic Ustochrept) with pH 8.2, EC 0.15 dS/m, organic C 0.34%, total N 0.06% Olsen's P 10 kg/ha, and a percolation rate of 5 mm/h.

Sesbania grown in situ for 7 wk was incorporated 1 d before transplanting. Sesbania dry matter was 24 t/ha, with

Sesbania plus N effects on yield. Ludhiana, India, 1986 kharif.

Treatment	N application (kg/ha) at indicated time			Grain yield (t/ha)
	0 DT	21 DT	42 DT	
No sesbania + no N	—	—	—	4.8
No sesbania + 120 kg N/ha	40	40	40	7.4
No sesbania + 180 kg N/ha	60	60	60	8.2
Sesbania + no N	—	—	—	7.0
Sesbania + 60 kg N/ha	60	—	—	8.1
Sesbania + 60 kg N/ha	—	60	—	7.8
Sesbania + 60 kg N/ha	30	—	30	8.1
Sesbania + 60 kg N/ha	30	30	—	7.7
Sesbania + 60 kg N/ha	—	30	30	8.4
Sesbania + 120 kg N/ha	—	60	60	8.4
Sesbania + 120 kg N/ha	40	40	40	9.0
LSD (P = 0.05)				0.4

106 kg N/ha. All plots received 26 kg P and 23 kg K/ha at the final puddling. Sesbania green manure plus 60 kg N/ha yielded more than sesbania with 120 kg N/ha (see table). Applying 60 kg N/ha

in 2 equal splits at 21 d and 42 d after transplanting (DT) was most efficient.

If 120 kg N/ha is applied with green manure, 3 equal splits at 0, 21, and 42 DT gave the highest yield. □

Responses of rice to N, P, and Zn in semireclaimed alkali soil

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P deficiency has been a major cause of low yields in semireclaimed alkali soils. We studied the effect of P fertilization with N and Zn in a semireclaimed alkali

Effect of P application with N and Zn on yield in a semireclaimed alkali soil. Karnal, India.

Treatment (kg/ha)	Grain yield (t/ha)		
	Zero	17.5 kg P	Mean
N 120 Z 0	4.9	5.2	5.0
N 160 Z 0	5.2	5.3	5.2
N 80 Z 20	4.5	5.0	4.8
N 120 Z 20	5.4	6.6	6.0
N 160 Z 20	5.8	7.5	6.6
N 200 Z 20	5.7	7.1	6.4
Mean	5.2	6.1	
LSD (0.05)			
N		0.72	
P		0.36	
N × P		ns	

soil. The experiment was laid out in a split-plot design with four replications.

Half the N and all the P and Zn were applied at transplanting as urea, single superphosphate, and zinc sulfate. The remaining N was topdressed in 2 equal splits at 3 and 6 wk after transplanting. Recommended agronomic practices were followed.

Originally the soil had been highly sodic (pH 10.45), but gypsum application and 4 yr cropping had reduced pH to 8.8, EC to 0.42 dS/m,

and exchangeable sodium percentage to 19 in 0-15 cm surface soil. The soil had loamy texture, 0.28% organic C, 2.73% CaCO₃, 0.5 mg DTPA-Zn/kg, 76 mg available N, 3.96 mg available P, and 140 mg available K/kg.

Applying N and Zn without P had no effect on yield. Applying N, P, and Zn together significantly increased yield (see table). A balanced application of 160 kg N, 17.5 kg P, and 4.5 kg Zn/ha gave the maximum yield. □

Effects of several urea-based N sources

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We compared 6 urea sources — prilled urea (PU), urea supergranule (USG), large granule urea (LGU), neem cake-coated urea (NCU), rock phosphate-

coated urea (RPU), and sulfur-coated urea (SCU) — at 37.5, 112.5, and 150 kg N/ha in a 1986 dry season field experiment. Soil was a fine loamy hyperthermic Typic Haplaquept with pH 5.3, organic C 0.46%, CEC 4.3 meq/100 g, 215 kg available N/ha (alk. permanganate method), 6.5 kg available P/ha (NaHCO₃ extract), and 37 kg available K/ha (ammonium acetate extract). The experiment was in a split-

plot design with N in the main plots and sources in the subplots.

Seedlings of Lalat (Obs 677/IR2071//Vikram/W1263, 130d duration group) were transplanted on 22 Jan. All plots received 22 kg P and 41 kg K/ha with all the LGU, NCU, RPU, SCU, and 1/3 the PU at transplanting. All the USG was placed 7 cm deep at 10 d after transplanting (DT). The additional PU was applied in equal splits at 20 DT and at panicle initiation.

Yields increased significantly with increasing N up to 112.5 kg N/ha (Table 1), although yield response (kg grain/kg N) and apparent N recovery values (Table 2) were highest at 37.5 kg N. Yields with USG and SCU were equal and significantly superior to those with other N sources. USG at 75 kg N/ha was the best treatment, as is reflected in yield response and apparent N recovery. □

Table 1. Grain yield with urea-based N sources. Bhubaneswar, India, 1986 dry season.

Nitrogen dose (kg/ha)	Yield (t/ha)						
	PU	USG	LGU	NCU	RPU	SCU	Mean
0	2.2	2.1	2.2	2.3	2.1	2.4	2.2
37.5	3.4	4.3	3.5	3.9	3.9	3.7	3.8
75.0	4.5	5.5	4.4	4.3	3.9	5.0	4.6
112.5	5.5	5.5	4.7	5.1	5.3	6.2	5.4
150.0	5.6	5.5	5.5	5.5	5.3	5.5	5.5
Mean	4.2	4.6	4.0	4.2	4.1	4.5	4.3
LSD (0.05) N:0.6, Source: 0.3. Sources at fixed N: 0.7 and N at the same or different source: 0.9							

Table 2. Yield response and apparent N recovery with urea-based N sources. Bhubaneswar, India, 1986 dry season.

Nitrogen dose (kg/ha)	Yield response (kg grain/kg N)	Apparent N recovery (%)	Source		
			Yield response (kg grain/kg N)	Apparent N recovery (%)	
37.5	41.6	51.4	PU	28.0	44.7
75.0	31.7	39.3	USG	38.1	54.2
112.5	28.0	42.7	LGU	26.6	32.6
150.0	21.7	40.2	NCU	30.1	41.9
			RPU	28.6	39.5
			SCU	33.1	47.5

Effect of urea supergranule (USG) on grain yield of varieties of different durations

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We studied the influence of USG on varieties of different durations in controlled irrigated experiments 1984-

85. Recommended P, K, and Zn were applied before field puddling, N was applied as per treatment. The soil was a Vertisol type with pH 8.2, CEC 49.2 meq/ 100 g soil, 0.09% total N, and 5 ppm available P.

Short-duration (95-105 d) IET7564, IET7613, IET7614, and IET7566 were evaluated with 90 kg N/ ha using USG placement and prilled urea split application. Source of N was not significant (3.94.4 t/ha).

In longduration (150-165 d) IET5897, IET5890, IET5656, Jagannath, Phalgun, and Pankaj, 90 kg N/ ha as urea best split was superior or equal to USG placement at 7 d after transplanting (DT). Yields with 3/4 N as USG at 7 DT + 1/4 N as prilled urea at panicle initiation were significantly greater than yields with prilled urea best split (Table 1).

Medium-duration Rasi responded better to USG (90 kg N/ha) than to prilled urea and other coated materials (Table 2). □

Table 1. Mean grain yield of irrigated six long-duration varieties with USG and split applications of prilled urea. Andhra Pradesh, India, 1984-85.

Treatment	Grain yield (t/ha)	
	1984	1985
Best split (prilled urea)	5.8	4.9
Four splits (prilled urea)	5.3	4.6
USG at 7 DT	5.5	5.1
1/4 N as prilled urea (basal) + 3/4 N as USG at 28 DT	-	5.1
3/4 N as USG at 7 DT + 1/4 N as prilled urea at panicle initiation	-	5.3
CD (0.05)	0.3	0.2
CV (%)	7.1	6.8

Table 2. Effect of modified urea materials on grain yield of Rasi. Andhra Pradesh, India, 1984 kharif.

Treatment	Grain yield (t/ha)
Urea best split	4.6
USG at 7 DT	5.8
Mussoorie-phos-coated urea	4.8
Gypsum-coated urea	4.8
Neem cake-coated urea	4.4
Urea 4 equal splits (1/4 N basal + 1/4 N before panicle initiation + 1/4 N after panicle initiation + 1/4 N panicle stage)	4.5
Compost + USG (1/2 N as USG)	4.8
CD (0.05)	0.8
CV (%)	9.4

Mussoorie rock phosphate (MRP) effects on yield

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MRP is an indigenous fertilizer material suitable for acid soils; it slowly and continuously releases available P.

We studied its availability to rice variety Phalgun in a field experiment